

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel formazans incorporating pyrimidine ring

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Abstract : Reaction of 5-substituted-4(3*H*)-one-2-mercaptopyrimidines **1a** and **1b** with hydrazine hydrate furnishes 5-substituted-4(3*H*)-one-2-hydrazinopyrimidines **2a** and **2b**. Condensation of compounds **2a** and **2b** with salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde yields 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde-(5'-substituted-4'(3*H*)-one)-2'-pyrimidazolylhydrazones) **3a** and **3b** and 4-methoxybenzaldehyde-(5'-substituted-4'(3*H*)-one)-2'-pyrimidazolylhydrazones) **3c** and **3d** respectively. Compounds **3a-d** were reacted with diazonium salts of an appropriate primary amine in presence of base furnished the target formazans **4a-l**. All the synthesized compounds were evaluated for antimicrobial activities.

Keywords : Pyrimidine analogs, formazans, antimicrobial agents.

Introduction

The biological significance of the pyrimidine analogs has led to synthesize substituted pyrimidines. Many of the Schiff bases containing pyrimidine system exhibit anticancer and antitubercular activities¹ as well as antimicrobial activities^{2,3}. Pyrimidines impart diverse pharmacological properties such as, insecticidal⁴, antitumour⁵, herbicidal⁶, antiviral⁷, antifungal⁸ and anti-malarial⁹ activities. In the course of investigations, formazans were found to exhibit antiviral^{10,11}, antibacterial^{12,13} and anti-inflammatory¹⁴ activities. Formazans were also used for analytical purposes, particularly in trace element determinations¹⁵. We have also found in literature versatile synthetic routes for the synthesis of formazans derived from various heterocyclic moieties^{15,16}. These findings concerning importance of pyrimidine moiety in biological system and biological activities of formazans, prompted us to synthesize Schiff bases as synthons for the synthesis of formazans incorporating a pyrimidine ring as potential pharmacological agents.

Results and discussion

Formazans were synthesized in three steps starting from 5-substituted-4(3*H*)-one-2-mercaptopyrimidines **1a** and **1b** (Scheme 1) (Table 1). Reaction of **1a** and **1b** with hydrazine hydrate (99%) under reflux for 8 h

furnishes the desired 5-substituted-4(3*H*)-one-2-hydrazinopyrimidines **2a** and **2b**. Compound **2b** was obtained in 78% yield as a white crystalline solid having m.p. 220–221 °C. The IR spectrum of compound **2b** shows absorption frequencies at 3267, 3210 and 3019 cm⁻¹ due to NH, 1644 cm⁻¹ due to C=O and 1594 cm⁻¹ due to C=N. The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2b** exhibited a broad singlet at δ 11.8 due to the resonance of proton of lactam NH of uracil ring. The single proton present on the pyrimidine moiety of C₆-position has been found to be resonated at δ 7.3. The NH and NH₂ hydrazine were resonated at δ 6.0 and 5.3 respectively. Methyl group protons at C₅-position of uracil were resonated as a sharp singlet at δ 1.75. Further, the structure of compound **2b** was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : C, 42.83; H, 5.70; N, 39.98. Calcd. for C₅H₈N₄O : C, 42.85; H, 5.71; N, 40.00%).

Compounds **2a** and **2b** on condensation with salicylaldehyde and anisaldehyde in refluxing methanol for 3–5 h in presence of a catalytic amount of hydrogen chloride furnishes the Schiff bases **3a-d** respectively. Compound **3a** was obtained in 72% yield as yellow crystalline solid having m.p. 190–191 °C. The IR spectrum of compound **3a** shows characteristic absorptions at 3368 cm⁻¹ due to OH functionality, at 3110 and 2945 cm⁻¹ due to NH functional group, at 2761 cm⁻¹ due to CH stretching, at 1626 cm⁻¹ due to the

Table 1. Physical data of synthesized compounds 2-4 (Scheme 1)

Compd	R	R'	R''	M.p. ^a (°C)	Yield ^b (%)
2a	H	–	–	215–217	85
2b	CH ₃	–	–	220–221	78
3a	H	OH(<i>o</i>)	–	190–191	72
3b	H	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	–	165–166	80
3c	CH ₃	OH(<i>o</i>)	–	192–193	70
3d	CH ₃	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	–	255–257	75
4a	H	OH(<i>o</i>)	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	185–186	55
4b	H	OH(<i>o</i>)	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	140–142	52
4c	H	OH(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	208–210	65
4d	H	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	146–147	50
4e	H	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	180–183	42
4f	H	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	160–161	68
4g	CH ₃	OH(<i>o</i>)	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	190–191	55
4h	CH ₃	OH(<i>o</i>)	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	122–123	50
4i	CH ₃	OH(<i>o</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	215–217	63
4j	CH ₃	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	125–126	50
4k	CH ₃	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	120–121	45
4l	CH ₃	OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Cl(<i>p</i>)	130–131	65

^aMelting points are uncorrected. ^bYield refers to purified product.

carbonyl group and peaks at 1573, 1555 cm⁻¹ due to C=N stretching. ¹H NMR spectrum of **3a** exhibited a broad singlet at δ 13.4 due to the resonance of a proton of NH of lactam ring. The hydroxy group proton of salicylaldehyde resonates as singlet at δ 10.9. The NH of hydrazine resonates at δ 8.6 as a singlet. The proton at C₆ carbon of uracil has resonated at δ 8.1 as a doublet. The multiplet from δ 7.5–6.8 is due to four aromatic protons. The singlet appeared at δ 6.4 for azomethine proton. Another doublet at δ 5.9 is due to a single proton of C₅ carbon of uracil. Further, the structure of compound **3a** was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : C, 57.37; H, 4.33; N, 24.33. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀N₄O₂ : C, 57.39; H, 4.34; N, 24.34%).

Compounds **3a-d** on coupling with aryldiazonium chlorides of an appropriate aryl amine in pyridine maintaining the reaction mixture below 5 °C afforded the desired 2,5-disubstituted pyrimidine analogs **4a-l**. Compound **4a** was obtained in 55% yield as a brown crystalline solid having m.p. 185–186 °C. The IR spectrum of compound **4a** shows characteristic absorp-

tions of OH 3107, NH 2965, 2833, C=O 1635, C=N 1599, 1504, N=N 1484 cm⁻¹. Further, the structure of compound **4a** was confirmed by the ¹H NMR spectrum. The characteristic signals are at δ 12.2 (1H, s, NH), 10.8 (1H, s, OH), 8.5 (1H, s, NH), 7.8 (1H, d, C₆H), 7.6–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, d, C₅H), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃). The IR spectrum of compound **4a** indicates the absence of absorption at 2850 cm⁻¹ and in ¹H NMR spectrum disappearance of singlet at δ 6.4 (1H, s, N=CH) indicates the successful condensation of aryldiazonium chlorides with azomethine group. Further, the structure of compound **4a** was confirmed by elemental analysis (Found : C, 65.05; H, 4.79; N, 25.29. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆N₆O₂ : C, 65.06; H, 4.81; N, 25.30%).

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of compounds **2-4** (Table 2) was studied comparatively with that of standard antibiotic, gentamycin, by cup-plate method¹⁷ using two gram negative organisms namely, *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and two gram positive organisms, namely *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of compounds 2-4 (Scheme 1)

Compd.	Dose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Antibacterial activity Zone of inhibition (mm)			
		<i>E. coli</i> (Gram -ve)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (Gram -ve)	<i>B. subtilus</i> (Gram +ve)	<i>S. aureus</i> (Gram +ve)
2a	1000	10	11	11	10
2b	1000	12	13	10	14
3a	1000	12	11	22	14
3b	1000	8	10	8	8
3c	1000	11	14	14	13
3d	1000	10	10	10	10
4a	1000	13	11	13	13
4b	1000	11	10	14	10
4c	1000	12	13	12	14
4d	1000	11	13	13	13
4e	1000	13	10	12	10
4f	1000	12	11	10	11
4g	1000	10	12	13	12
4h	1000	12	10	12	12
4i	1000	14	8	10	8
4j	1000	8	9	8	8
4k	1000	10	13	13	13
4l	1000	14	11	12	12
Gentamycin	1000	23	24	23	23
Control (DMF)	-	0	0	0	0

The antibacterial activity revealed that compound 3a exhibited good antibacterial activity against *B. subtilus*, compound 4c exhibited good antibacterial activity against *E. coli*. Remaining compounds exhibited poor antibacterial activity against all bacterial strains used for our evaluation.

Antifungal activity :

The antifungal activity of compounds 2-4 (Table 3) was studied in comparison with that of standard antifungal drug flucanazole by cup plate method¹⁸. The fungal strains selected for this were *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus* and *P. chrysogenum*.

The antifungal activity revealed that compounds 4e, 4h and 4n exhibited good antifungal activity against *A. flavus*. Compounds 3c, 3d and 4n exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *A. niger*. Compounds 4f, 4i and 4m exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *A. flavus*. Compounds 4k and 4m exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *A. fumigatus*. Compound 4g

exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *P. chrysogenum*. Remaining compounds exhibited weak antifungal activity against all fungal strains used for our evaluation.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes in paraffin oil bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr disc were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Spectrum-one FTIR spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) and ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆ on amx 400, 400 MHz spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δ , ppm). Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel 'G' plates obtained from Whatman Inc, and a fluorescent indicator.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5-substituted-4(3H)-one-2-hydrazinopyrimidines (2a and 2b) :

A mixture of 5-substituted-4(3H)-one-2-mercapto-pyrimidine 1a or 1b (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99%, 0.051 mol) were refluxed for 8–10 h and cooled

to room temperature. The separated crystals were filtered and washed with small amount of spirit, dried and recrystallization from MeOH yielded the desired compounds **2a** or **2b**.

2-Hydrazino-4(3H)-one-pyrimidine 2a : Yield : 5.3 g (85%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3250, 3205, 3010 (NH), 1650 (C=O), 1590 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 11.8 (1H, s, NH), 7.12 (1H, d, C_6H), 5.7 (1H, d, C_5H), 5.5 (1H, s, NH), 4.8 (2H, s, NH_2) (Found : C, 38.08; H, 4.74; N, 44.43. Calcd. for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 38.09; H, 4.76; N, 44.44%).

5-Methyl-4(3H)-one-2-hydrazinopyrimidine 2b : Yield : 5.4 g (78%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3267, 3210, 3019 (NH), 1644 (C=O), 1594 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 11.8 (1H, s, NH), 7.2 (1H, s, C_6H), 6.0 (1H, s, NH), 5.3 (2H, s, NH_2), 1.75 (3H, s, CH_3) (Found : C, 42.83; H, 5.70; N, 39.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 42.85; H, 5.71; N, 40.00%).

General procedure for the synthesis of Schiff bases (3a-d) :

A mixture of **2a-d** (0.02 mol) and appropriate aldehydes (0.021 mol) in methanol (100 ml) containing 3-4 drops of conc. HCl were refluxed on a water-bath for 3-5 h and cooled. The crystalline solid, which separated out during reaction, was filtered and recrystallized from methanol, to give the desired compounds **3a-d**.

2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde-4'(3'H)-one-2'-pyrimidazolyldrazone 3a : Yield : 3.3 g (72%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3368 (OH), 3110, 2945 (NH), 2761 (CH), 1626 (C=O), 1573, 1555 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 13.3 (1H, s, NH), 10.9 (1H, s, OH), 8.6 (1H, s, NH), 8.1 (1H, d, C_6H), 7.5-6.8 (4H, m, ArH), 6.4 (1H, s, CH), 5.9 (1H, d, C_5H) (Found : C, 57.37; H, 4.33; N, 24.33. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 57.39; H, 4.34; N, 24.34%).

4-Methoxybenzaldehyde-4'(3'H)-one-2'-pyrimidazolyldrazone 3b : Yield : 3.9 g (80%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3100, 2950 (NH), 2760 (CH), 1640 (C=O), 1579, 1560 (C=N), 1267 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 13.0 (1H, s, NH), 8.5 (1H, s, NH), 8.1 (1H, d, C_6H), 7.5-6.8 (4H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, s, CH), 5.7 (1H, d, C_5H), 4.3 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 59.00; H, 4.89; N, 22.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 59.01; H, 4.91; N, 22.95%).

2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde-(5'-methyl-4'(3'H)-one)-2'-pyrimidazolyldrazone 3c : Yield : 3.4 g (70%); IR

(cm^{-1}) : 3370 (OH), 3108, 2947 (NH), 2750 (CH), 1630 (C=O), 1571, 1550 (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 13.0 (1H, s, NH), 10.8 (1H, s, OH), 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 8.5 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.5-7.2 (4H, m, ArH), 6.4 (1H, s, CH), 1.8 (3H, s, CH_3) (Found : C, 58.98; H, 4.88; N, 22.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 59.01; H, 4.91; N, 22.95%).

4-Methoxybenzaldehyde-(5'-methyl-4'(3'H)-one)-2'-pyrimidazolyldrazone 3d : Yield : 3.8 g (75%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3203, 2923 (NH/NH), 2854 (CH), 1617 (C=O), 1573, 1525 (C=N), 1266 (C-O-C); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 13.0 (1H, s, NH), 8.7 (1H, s, NH), 8.5 (1H, s, C_6H), 7.5-7.3 (4H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, s, CH), 4.3 (3H, s, OCH_3), 1.8 (3H, s, CH_3) (Found : C, 60.44; H, 5.40; N, 21.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$: C, 60.46; H, 5.42; N, 21.70%).

General procedure for the synthesis of formazans (4a-l) :

The diazonium salt solution of an appropriate arylamine (0.0015 mol) was added dropwise with continuous stirring to a solution of **3a-d** (0.001 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) maintaining the temperature of the reaction mixture below 5 °C. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and poured into ice-cold water (25 ml) with continuous stirring. The dark colored solid thus separated, was filtered and washed with cold water followed by hot water, dried well in air and recrystallized from EtOH to give the desired compounds **4a-l**.

1-(p-Methylphenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4a : Yield : 0.19 g (55%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3107 (OH), 2965, 2833 (NH/NH), 1635 (C=O), 1599, 1504 (C=N), 1484 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.2 (1H, s, NH), 10.8 (1H, s, OH), 8.5 (1H, s, NH), 7.8 (1H, d, C_6H), 7.6-6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 6.3 (1H, d, C_5H), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3) (Found : C, 65.05; H, 4.79; N, 25.29. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$: C, 65.06; H, 4.81; N, 25.30%).

1-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4b : Yield : 0.19 g (52%); IR (cm^{-1}) : 3230 (OH), 3099 (NH/NH), 1619 (C=O), 1487 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.3 (1H, s, NH), 10.9 (1H, s, OH), 8.6 (1H, s, NH), 8.4 (1H, d, C_6H), 8.0-6.5 (8H, m, ArH), 6.0 (1H, d, C_5H), 4.5 (3H, s, OCH_3) (Found : C, 59.33; H, 4.38; N, 23.06. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3$: C, 59.34; H, 4.39; N, 23.07%).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4c : Yield : 0.23 g (65%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3435 (OH), 2923 (NH/NH), 1637 (C=O), 1484 (N=N); ¹H NMR : δ 12.3 (1H, s, NH), 10.0 (1H, s, OH), 8.8 (1H, d, C₆H), 7.8 (1H, s, NH), 7.5–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 6.0 (1H, d, C₅H) (Found : C, 55.42; H, 3.52; N, 22.81. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₃N₆O₂Cl : C, 55.43; H, 3.53; N, 22.82%).

1-(p-Methylphenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4d : Yield : 0.18 g (50%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3165 (OH), 2935 (NH/NH), 1660 (C=O), 1461 (N=N); ¹H NMR : δ 12.3 (1H, s, NH), 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 8.0 (1H, d, C₆H), 7.8–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 5.4 (1H, d, C₅H), 4.2 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃)

(Found : C, 62.97; H, 4.96; N, 23.18. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₂ : C, 62.98; H, 4.97; N, 23.20%).

1-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4e : Yield : 0.15 g (42%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3065 (NH/NH), 1645 (C=O), 1445 (N=N); ¹H NMR : δ 12.1 (1H, s, NH), 9.0 (1H, s, NH), 8.6 (1H, d, C₆H), 8.1–7.0 (8H, m, ArH), 5.6 (1H, d, C₅H), 4.5 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.3 (3H, s, OCH₃) (Found : C, 60.30; H, 4.74; N, 22.20. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₃ : C, 60.31; H, 4.76; N, 22.22%).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-5-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4f : Yield : 0.25 g (68%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3094, 2933 (NH), 1606 (C=O), 1580, 1512 (C=N), 1462 (N=N), 1309, 1254 (C–O–C), 830

Scheme 1

Table 3. Antifungal activity of compounds 2-4 (Scheme 1)

Compd.	Dose ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Antifungal activity Zone of inhibition (mm)			
		<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>
2a	1000	12	12	10	15
2b	1000	11	10	11	16
3a	1000	13	11	10	14
3b	1000	12	12	12	14
3c	1000	16	10	11	14
3d	1000	18	10	11	15
4a	1000	14	12	12	13
4b	1000	12	12	10	11
4c	1000	6	10	12	12
4d	1000	8	11	12	10
4e	1000	10	20	10	15
4f	1000	10	16	10	14
4g	1000	12	12	10	16
4h	1000	12	20	11	15
4i	1000	10	16	12	15
4j	1000	8	14	13	14
4k	1000	12	13	17	13
4l	1000	12	14	13	13
Fluconazole	1000	25	25	27	23
Control (DMF)	-	0	0	0	0

(C-Cl); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.1 (1H, s, NH), 9.2 (1H, s, NH), 8.5 (1H, d, C₆H), 7.5–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 6.1 (1H, d, C₅H), 4.2 (3H, s, OCH₃) (Found : C, 56.52; H, 3.91; N, 21.97. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅N₆O₂Cl : C, 56.54; H, 3.92; N, 21.98%).

1-(p-Methylphenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4g : Yield : 0.19 g (55%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3104 (OH), 2993 (NH), 1682 (C=O), 1562 (C=N), 1454 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.0 (1H, s, NH), 10.3 (1H, s, OH), 8.8 (1H, s, NH), 8.2 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.6–7.0 (8H, m, ArH), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.30 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 62.97; H, 4.96; N, 23.19. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₂ : C, 62.98; H, 4.97; N, 23.20%).

1-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4h : Yield : 0.18 g (50%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3357 (OH), 3068, 3050 (NH), 1678 (C=O), 1553, 1505 (C=N), 1459 (N=N), 1254 (C–O–C); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.1 (1H, s, NH), 9.9 (1H, s, OH), 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 8.4 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.4–6.5 (8H, m, ArH), 4.3 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.70 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 60.30; H, 4.75; N, 22.21. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O₃ : C, 60.31; H, 4.76; N, 22.22%).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(o-hydroxyphenyl)formazan 4i : Yield : 0.24 g (63%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3195 (OH), 3065 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1587 (C=N), 1483 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.0 (1H, s, NH), 9.7 (1H, s, OH), 9.0 (1H, s, NH), 8.5 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.2–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 1.8 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 56.52; H, 3.90; N, 21.97. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅N₆O₂Cl : C, 56.54; H, 3.92; N, 21.98%).

1-(p-Methylphenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4j : Yield : 0.18 g (50%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3150, 3035 (NH), 1660 (C=O), 1580, 1511 (C=N), 1460 (N=N), 1258 (C–O–C); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 12.9 (1H, s, NH), 8.6 (1H, s, NH), 8.2 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.4–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.82 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 63.80; H, 5.30; N, 22.32. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₆O₂ : C, 63.82; H, 5.31; N, 22.34%).

1-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-(4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4k : Yield : 0.17 g (45%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3294, 3093 (NH), 1606 (C=O), 1585, 1512 (C=N), 1484 (N=N), 1254, 1250

(C–O–C); ¹H NMR : δ 12.0 (1H, s, NH), 8.7 (1H, s, NH), 8.0 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.8–7.2 (8H, m, ArH), 4.4 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.7 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 61.20; H, 5.08; N, 21.40. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₆O₃ : C, 61.22; H, 5.10; N, 21.42%).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-5-(5'-methyl-4'(3'H)-one-pyrimidin-2'-yl)-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)formazan 4I : Yield : 0.25 g (65%); IR (cm⁻¹) : 3110, 3040 (NH), 1606 (C=O), 1585, 1512 (C=N), 1470 (N=N), 1253 (C–O–C), 771 (C–Cl); ¹H NMR : δ 12.6 (1H, s, NH), 9.1 (1H, s, NH), 8.2 (1H, s, C₆H), 7.8–6.8 (8H, m, ArH), 4.3 (3H, s, OCH₃), 1.75 (3H, s, CH₃) (Found : C, 57.55; H, 4.27; N, 21.20. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₃N₆O₂Cl : C, 57.57; H, 4.29; N, 21.21%).

References

- 1 J Sengupta, *Indian J Appl Chem*, 1964, 3, 29
- 2 F D Popp, *J Org Chem*, 1961, 26, 1560
- 3 V K Ahulwalia, N Kalia and S Bala, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1987, 26, 700
- 4 D B Scott, M Nair, T L K Ulbrich, M L Roger and E C Chu, *Rose Cancer Res* 1959, 19, 15
- 5 K M Youssef, A H Abou-Sten, M V H Essawi and S Shouman, *Egypt J Pharm Sci*, 1944, 35, 383
- 6 *Chem Abstr*, 1994, 120, 107046t
- 7 Archana, Joyti Shrivastava, Sanjay Swarup, V K Saxena and B L Chowdhury, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1991, 68, 658
- 8 N M Goudgaon and A Vijayalaxmi, *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2003, 65, 545
- 9 E A Falco, L G Goodwin, G H Hitchings, I M Rollo and P B Russel, *Brit J Pharmacol* 1951, 6, 185
- 10 J N Ashley, B M Davis, A W Nineham and R Slack, *J Chem Soc* 1953, 3881
- 11 R Kuhn and D Jerchel, *Chem Ber* 1941, 74, 941
- 12 D D Mukherjee and S K Shukla, *J Antibact Antifung Agents* 1981, 9, 521
- 13 H G Garg and M Kaur, *J Med Chem* 1972, 15, 554
- 14 V S Misra, S Dhar and B L Chowdhury, *Pharmazie*, 1978, 33, 790
- 15 B N Lipunova, N N Gulemina and S L Mertsalov, *Zh Anal Khim*, 1977, 32, 1908
- 16 I Frysova, J Slouka and T Gucky, *Arxivoc* 2005, xv, 1
- 17 Indian Pharmacopoeia Controller of Publication, New Delhi, India, 1996, I, 344